

SOCIAL FACTORS OF INFORMAL EMPLOYMENT OF WOMEN IN UZBEKISTAN

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Today, one of the social factors of informal employment of women in Uzbekistan is that international migration creates strong flows compared to internal migration. As a result, receiving countries face financial problems in accommodating women and children, who are relatively vulnerable groups of migrants, and in creating the necessary social conditions for them.

In particular, the number of social problems among the part of women who are involved in the informal employment of labor migration is increasing. Such problems leave a deep mark not only on women's work, but also on their family life. In particular, the number of women suffering from such problems is increasing in societies based on traditional family-marriage relations. Although migration improves the financial situation of separated families, older members of the family, especially women, are not sufficiently engaged in raising children due to constant employment. As a result, the risk of deviance among children of migrants increases. Due to mass, irregular migrations on the state level, the sanitary-epidemiological situation worsens as a result of its political, demographic and economic consequences. Women and children are the main victims of this situation.

Today, the countries that accept migrants at the international level to ensure the informal employment of women in Uzbekistan are the USA, European countries, Latin America, South-East Asian countries, South-Eastern Asia, Israel, and almost 70% of the labor force demand in these countries is filled by migrants. In the list of countries that supply labor force in the global cocktail market, India, Pakistan, Algeria, Mexico, Ireland, Turkey and the CIS countries have a large share, says the agency of the women-girls' employment provision agency.

Currently, according to UN statistics, the intensity of overpopulation has increased beyond control. In relation to different periods of human history, a large part of the world's population lives in developed countries, not in stagnant countries. According to the latest data, the number of international migrants in 2023 was 272 million. reached In 2018, this figure was 173 million. International experts are worried that this indicator has increased to 100

million in a short time. It is noteworthy that women make up 48% of the total share of migrants, while 38 mln. Children are active participants in this process.

Due to the efforts of international organizations, the principle of "fair migration" is used in the regulation and management of modern migration processes. This principle was developed by the International Labor Organization in 2014, and the main issue in the modern migration flow was the strict adherence to the principles of justice in the treatment of migrants. Respecting the human rights and social protection of migrant workers, creating suitable conditions for working and living for them, according to the program based on this principle, was made a priority task. However, 141 mln. migrants settled in European and North American countries. Out of 50 million of them, the rest is only one share of the United States.

On December 12, 2018, the Constitution of the International Organization for Migration was ratified as a logical continuation of the measures implemented in our republic to protect the social interests of labor migrants. At the same time, a plan of measures for the development of cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the International Organization for Migration in 2022 was developed. This step included our republic in the ranks of 173 member and 8 observer states of the International Organization for Migration and ensured its participation in the activities aimed at protecting the social rights of migrants.

The work on the protection of the social interests of the participants of labor migration, which provides informal employment of women in Uzbekistan, has been further improved, and on August 20, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of the protection of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their family members engaged in temporary labor activities abroad" was adopted. . In this document, in addition to ensuring the protection of the rights and interests of citizens going abroad for temporary work, a number of tasks were defined in terms of creating suitable conditions for the living and working of labor migrants and their family members. In addition, comprehensive measures were developed, providing for the creation of mechanisms of social support in matters of housing, improvement of living conditions, financial assistance, protection of life and safety for migrant workers and their family members. In this, the main attention was paid to the trends in the tune:

- Social factors of informal employment among women in Uzbekistan are the globalization of migration flows. In this case, almost all countries are

surrounded, and in the countries where immigration or emigration is the priority, the social consequences of women's labor migration differ;

- qualitative changes are being observed in the course of women's labor migration, the share of female migrants with high qualification and professional competence level is increasing;

- increasing women's labor migration to the level of personal choice, not just for material benefit;

- Strengthening and regulation of migration policy as a result of increasing social consequences of women's labor migration.

In the era of the information revolution, women feel more about their rights and opportunities, and their confidence in social and working life is increasing. This trend has increased women's educational opportunities in most developed and developing countries, thereby increasing their professional and employment opportunities. Higher education of women creates the basis for increasing their activity in the labor market. Based on the above, it can be noted that the expanded opportunities of women in all spheres of social life have moved to a new qualitative stage of female employment.

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